

shown to be dependant on the nature of the solvent, nature of x and also deviation from trigonal bipyramidal geometry^{15,16}. In the present complex, another dimension to the problem is added by the fact that the two bidentate ligands are different. This will bring down the symmetry still further. Thus the high extinction coefficient and splitting of the band just show probable pentacoordination.

The visible spectra of the compounds containing β -ketoanilide show a broad band in the region ~ 600 nm with molar absorbance (~ 88). This broad band is a combination of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{1g}$ transitions¹⁷, corresponding to D_{4h} symmetry, most probably square planar in these cases.

In the IR spectra of the compounds, bands in the region ~ 3400 cm^{-1} are absent indicating that water

The free perchlorate ion gives rise to two IR bands. A weak band at ~ 920 cm^{-1} due to the symmetrical stretching mode ν_1 , which is strictly IR forbidden, and ν_3 the asymmetrical stretching mode at ~ 1100 cm^{-1} which is IR allowed. When perchlorate is coordinated¹⁸ to a metal ion its symmetry is lowered from T_d to C_{3v} and thus symmetrical stretching becomes IR allowed and triple degeneracy of ν_3 is partly removed. Consequently the IR spectral band at ~ 920 cm^{-1} becomes more intense and ~ 1100 cm^{-1} band is resolved into two. In the present complexes containing β -diketones bands in both the regions ~ 960 cm^{-1} and ~ 1100 cm^{-1} are observed. This shows that the perchlorate is in the coordination sphere of these complexes(I).

The complexes containing β -ketoanilides(II) show a strong band at ~ 1100 cm^{-1} corresponding to asymmetric stretching in ClO_4^- . The band at ~ 920 cm^{-1} corresponding to symmetric stretch is absent. This shows that in the complexes(II) ClO_4^- ion has T_d symmetry and is ionic in nature.

No.	Name of the Complex	Metal%		Nitrogen%		μ in B.M	$\lambda_{max}(\epsilon)$ in Acetone	Conductance in methanol mhos cm^{-2} mol^{-1}
		Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found			
1	[Perchlorato, acetylacetonato, dipyriddy, Cu(II)]	15.19	15.32	6.69	6.73	1.87	580(4,10) 610(435)	—
2	[Perchlorato, acetylacetonato, o-phenanthroline Cu(II)]	18.81	18.68	6.09	6.12	1.81	590(364) 610(394)	—
3	[Perchlorato, benzoylacetonato, dipyriddy Cu(II)]	13.23	13.52	5.82	5.62	1.89	605(541) 620(577)	—
4	[Perchlorato, benzoylacetonato, o-phenanthroline Cu(II)]	12.17	12.52	5.36	5.43	1.83	600(511) 620(534)	—
5	[Perchlorato, dibenzoylmethanato, dipyriddy Cu(II)]	11.71	11.93	5.16	5.19	1.90	600(462) 620(487)	—
6	[Perchlorato, dibenzoylmethanato, o-phenanthroline Cu(II)]	10.88	10.57	4.79	4.62	1.78	600(442) 620(401)	—
7	[Acetoacetanilidato, dipyriddy Cu(II)] perchlorate	12.83	12.91	8.48	8.88	1.86	610(93)	102.87
8	[Acetoacetanilidato, o-phenanthroline Cu(II)] perchlorate	11.82	12.05	7.82	7.85	1.91	615(84)	103.18
9	[Acetoacet-o-toluidato, dipyriddy Cu(II)] perchlorate	12.47	12.17	8.25	8.20	2.04	610(86)	96.13
10	[Acetoacet-o-toluidato, o-phenanthroline Cu(II)] perchlorate	11.53	11.23	7.62	8.00	1.92	615(90)	108.61
11	[Acetoacet-o-anisididato, dipyriddy Cu(II)] perchlorate	12.10	12.31	8.00	8.02	1.94	595(95)	101.65
12	[Acetoacet-o-anisididato, o-phenanthroline Cu(II)] perchlorate	11.20	11.50	7.40	7.43	1.83	625(82)	96.52

is absent in these compounds. However, bands in the region ~ 3300 cm^{-1} is found in case of mixed complexes containing β -ketoanilides, corresponding to N-H stretching frequency of the anilide. Bands in the region ~ 1590 cm^{-1} correspond to $C=O$ stretch of the π bonded β -diketone.

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